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White List of Ranked Far-Future Accelerator Options

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ABSTRACT

Worldwide several novel accelerator technologies and future collider scenarios are being proposed along with possible advanced scientific applications. Among these are photon colliders, the Gamma factory, two versions of muon colliders, the use of plasmas, crystals or nanotubes for bending or acceleration, and employing storage rings or other accelerator technologies for the detection or acceleration of gravitational waves. Based on the results of six ARIES workshops, and through an online survey of the workshop participants, a ranking of far-future accelerator options has been performed, with regard to importance, maturity, potential impact on society, risk of failure and time scale for practical realization. Here, we present the resulting White List of Ranked Far-Future Accelerator Options, with recommendations for high-priority R&D foci and the expected time scales for practical realizations.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

A variety of future accelerator technologies and collider scenarios are being proposed along with possible advanced applications in different fields of physics research. Over the four years from 2017 to 2021, ARIES Work Package 6 “Accelerator Performance and Concepts” (APEC) has organized several targeted workshops, both in person and virtual, which examined many of these options and proposals, such as photon colliders, the Gamma factory, muon colliders with either proton- or positron-based muon production, the use of plasmas, crystals or nanotubes for bending or acceleration, and employing storage rings or other accelerator technologies for the detection or acceleration of gravitational waves. Based on the results of these ARIES workshops, and through an online survey of about 400 participants, about a quarter of whom responded, a ranking of far-future accelerator options could be performed. This survey considered, respectively, the importance, maturity, potential impact on society, risk of failure and time scale for practical realization of the different options.

Concerning future accelerators realizable about 15-30 years from now, the resulting White List of Ranked Far-Future Accelerator Options places a high priority, and suggests focusing R&D, on the following schemes: (1) Proton based muon collider, (2) Plasma acceleration, (3) Positron based muon collider, (4) Crystal and nanostructure acceleration, and, to some extent on (5) gravitational wave detection using storage rings.

For a shorter time scale, namely concerning accelerators that could be built during the next 10-15 years, the following approaches shall be pursued and realized with high priority: (1) energy recovery, (2) crystal bending, and (3) Gamma Factory.

Finally, low or no priority has been attributed to the following five options: (1) photon collider, (2) crystalline beams, (3) “Moessbauer acceleration” using photon entanglement, (4) gravitational wave generation using accelerators, and (5) non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms.

1. ARIES APEC Exploratory Workshops

From May 2017 to March 2021, ARIES Work Package 6 “Accelerator Performance and Concepts” (APEC) performed the following key workshops:

1. [Photon Beam workshop](#), Padova, Italy, 27-28 November 2017
2. [Muon Collider workshop](#), Padova, Italy, 2-3 July 2018
3. [First topical workshop on Beam Quality Control, Impedances and Reliability in Hadron Storage Rings & Synchrotrons \(APEC2018\)](#), Frankfurt am Main, Germany, 10-12 December 2018
4. [Accelerator Applications of Crystals and Nanotubes](#), hybrid workshop at EPFL in Lausanne, Switzerland, and in virtual space, 10-11 March 2020; summary report:

5. [Mitigation Approaches for Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons \(Mitigations2020\)](#), safe virtual space, 22 June – 1 July 2020; summary report:
6. [ARIES Workshop on Storage Rings and Gravitational Waves \(SRGW2021\)](#), safe virtual space, 2 February -18 March 2021

A total of about 400 different experts from around the world attended the above six workshops, which reviewed the state of the art and future prospects in an exploratory manner, with participation from other areas of science, like particle physics, astrophysics, and material sciences. The number of participants and their overall geographical distribution are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Total number of participants in each of the six key ARIES APEC workshops (left) and their overall geographical distribution (right).

In addition, it is worth noting that ARIES Work Package 6 “APEC” has also organized a number of workshops related to the theme of Energy Recovery:

- [LHeC/FCC-eh Workshop](#), CERN, Switzerland, 11-13 September 2017
- [LHeC, FCC-eh, and PERLE Workshop](#), LAL Orsay, France, 27-29 June, 2018
- [Electrons for the LHC](#), Chavannes-de-Bogis, Switzerland, 24-25 October 2019

The far-future accelerator options considered by ARIES WP6 are at different stages of development, and all require important R&D investments over several years to come to a technical design that could be used for implementation. As stated in the WP6 Workshops, their potential advantages with respect to more traditional particle colliders are huge, in terms of cost savings, wider scientific reach, and reduced impact on the environment, but the risks and challenges inherent with their R&D programme are also huge. The debate on these options within the particle accelerator and physics communities is of course very lively, leading to strong positions and conflicting messages.

The ARIES WP5 Workshops have contributed to examining in a fair and unbiased way the different options, and to submit them to the judgement of the scientific community. To try ranking them in terms of perceived feasibility, scientific priority, risk of failure, potential return to society, and time scale, following the end of the last workshop all participants from any of the above workshops were invited to answer an online survey. About a quarter of them (94 experts) responded. Most respondents

only rated a subset of options, according to their respective expertise. The two muon colliders, plasma acceleration and energy recovery attracted the largest numbers of votes.

2. Survey Options with References

The following options were examined. For each option, a few references and links are shown, which relate to, or might help explain, the respective concept. The list of references is far from comprehensive and our selection subjective.

- 1. Energy Recovery (>50 GeV and/or > 50 mA)^{1,2,3}**
- 2. Plasma Acceleration^{4,5,6}**
- 3. Photon Collider^{7,8,9}**
- 4. Gamma Factory^{10,11}**
- 5. Muon Collider, positron based^{12,13}**
- 6. Muon Collider, proton based^{14,15}**
- 7. Crystal or Nanostructure Acceleration^{16,17,18}**
- 8. Crystal Bending^{16,19}**
- 9. Crystalline Beams²⁰**
- 10. Gravitational Wave Detection using Storage Rings²¹**
- 11. Gravitational Wave Generation using Accelerators²¹**
- 12. High Energy Photon Generation using Entanglement and Moessbauer Effect²²**
- 13. Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms incl. gravity based schemes²²**

Further details on the above options, including a few brief descriptions, rough timelines, an indication of respective physics cases or possible impact on society, and additional references are given in Section 6.

3. Criteria and Possible Ratings

The rating criteria and possible answers offered are compiled in Table 1.

Table 1: ARIES survey criteria choices.

Feasibility	Importance/ Priority	Risk of Failure	Potential Return to Society	Time scale	Numeric ranking
Easy	Marginal	None	Negative	Next 5 years	1
Reachable	Relevant	Moderate	Marginal	Next 10 years	2
Difficult	High	High	Moderate	Next 20 years	3
Technically hard	Very high	Certain !	Strong	Next 40 years	4
Very challenging	Top		Game Changer !	Next 100 years	5
Impossible					6

4. Survey Respondents and Site Visitors

The survey invitation was sent to 388 different participants from the six ARIES exploratory workshops mentioned in Section 1. In total 94 experts responded. They hailed from the following countries and institutes: Austria (TU Wien Atominstitut), Belgium (Delft University of Technology), Brazil (UFCSPA), China, (Shanghai Advanced Research Institute Chinese Academy of Sciences, Institute of Modern Physics, Institute of High Energy Physics), France (ESRF, CEA/IRFU, LPNHE Paris Sorbonne), Germany (University of Hamburg, Max Planck Institute for Physics, GSI Darmstadt, Helmholtz Institute Mainz, Goethe University Frankfurt), Greece (National Technical University of Athens, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki), Italy (INFN Ferrara, INFN Pisa, INFN Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati, Sapienza Rome, INFN Roma), Japan (KEK, J-PARC, Hiroshima University), Portugal (LIP Lisbon), Russia (Landau Institute of Theoretical Physics, Budker INP), Sweden (ESS), Switzerland (CERN, University of Geneva), United Kingdom (RAL), and USA (Brookhaven National Laboratory, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, University of Colorado Denver, Stanford University, Fermilab, Jefferson Lab, Northern Illinois University, Communication and Power Industries (CPI), MUONS Inc.). The geographical distribution is shown in Fig. 2. The survey attracted quite some interest, as evidenced by the web site visits from various places around the world; see Fig. 3. A few representatives of industry involved in accelerator R&D took also part in the survey.

geographical distribution of survey respondents

Figure 2: Geographical distribution of survey respondents.

Figure 3: Countries of origin and number of visits to the ARIES future-option survey web site. A significant number of visitors were hiding the location of their IP address, indicated as “unknown”.

5. Rating Results

The full results of the community survey are summarized in the Appendix. However, the spectrum of the community response to each far-future option and the ranking of the proposed classes of relevance do not allow for a simple interpretation of the results. We, therefore, adopt the strategy of analyzing the results by assigning a weight to each rank (as indicated in last column of Table 1) and considering the average ranking plus standard deviation. We use this methodology to determine the most probable rank, with the rms value indicating the uncertainty of the community regarding this ranking. In Section 6, we will interpret the community survey results in light of what we, the coordinators, have learned and understood after 4 years of ARIES workshops.

Table 2 shows the results of the feasibility rating. Energy recovery, crystal bending and gamma factory are considered to be the most feasible options, while non-electromagnetic acceleration, gravitational wave generation using accelerators, and “Moessbauer acceleration” of entangled photons the least feasible.

Table 2: Feasibility - number of votes, average count (1: easy, 6: impossible – see Table 1) and rms spread.

Future Options	votes	average	rms
Energy Recovery (>50 GeV and/or > 50 mA)	65	2.75	0.96
Crystal bending	55	2.75	1.25
Gamma Factory	60	2.95	1.12
Photon Collider	58	3.53	1.15
Crystalline beams	47	3.57	1.25
Muon collider, proton based	68	3.72	1.06
Plasma Acceleration	67	3.88	1.25

Muon collider, positron based	65	4.02	1.13
Crystal or nanostructure acceleration	55	4.04	1.22
Gravitational wave detection using storage rings	49	4.59	1.07
High energy photon generation using entanglement and Moessbauer effect	35	4.60	0.80
Gravitational wave generation using accelerators	44	4.66	1.00
Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms including gravity based schemes	35	5.26	0.73

Table 3 presents the survey results concerning importance/priority. The two types of muon collider and plasma acceleration are the frontrunners in terms of priority. The least important schemes are crystalline beams, non-electromagnetic acceleration, gravitational wave generation using accelerators, and “Moessbauer acceleration” of entangled photons. Hence, our survey suggests that non-electromagnetic acceleration and Moessbauer acceleration are considered as neither feasible nor important.

Table 3: Importance / Priority - number of votes, average count (1: marginal, 5: top – see Table 1) and rms spread.

Future Options	votes	average	rms
Muon collider, proton based	68	3.22	1.16
Plasma Acceleration	67	3.15	1.14
Muon collider, positron based	65	2.94	1.10
Crystal or nanostructure acceleration	55	2.80	1.14
Energy Recovery (>50 GeV and/or > 50 mA)	65	2.72	0.97
Gamma Factory	60	2.63	1.01
Gravitational wave generation using accelerators	44	2.52	1.16
Gravitational wave detection using storage rings	49	2.49	1.15
Crystal bending	55	2.46	0.74
Photon Collider	58	2.19	0.80
High energy photon generation using entanglement and Moessbauer effect	35	2.14	1.07
Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms including gravity-based schemes	35	2.09	1.44
Crystalline beams	47	2.07	0.84

Table 4 shows the results for the risk of failure. Not surprisingly, the three choices with the highest risk of failure are identical to those considered least feasible, in Table 2. On the other end of the spectrum, the three lowest risk options correspond to the three most feasible approaches. For example, energy recovery is deemed to entail the lowest risk, and also to be the most feasible concept.

Table 4: Risk of Failure - number of votes, average count (1: none, 4: certain ! – see Table 1) and rms spread.

Future Options	votes	average	rms
Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms including gravity-based schemes	35	3.20	0.58
Gravitational wave generation using accelerators	44	3.09	0.56
High energy photon generation using entanglement and Moessbauer effect	35	3.00	0.59
Gravitational wave detection using storage rings	49	2.94	0.63
Muon collider, positron based	65	2.65	0.57
Plasma Acceleration	67	2.63	0.62
Crystal or nanostructure acceleration	55	2.63	0.62
Photon Collider	58	2.55	0.56
Crystalline beams	47	2.54	0.58
Muon collider, proton based	68	2.43	0.61
Gamma Factory	60	2.28	0.55
Crystal bending	55	2.17	0.60
Energy Recovery	65	2.00	0.40

Table 5 compiles the survey results on the return to society. Plasma acceleration and crystal or nanostructure accelerators offer the greatest potential return to society, followed by the two incarnations of muon collider. On the lowest ranks, we find Moessbauer acceleration, crystalline beams, and the photon collider.

Table 5: Potential return to society - number of votes, average count (1: negative, 5: game changer! – see Table 1) and rms spread.

Future Options	votes	average	rms
Plasma Acceleration	67	3.80	1.03
Crystal or nanostructure acceleration	55	3.62	1.01
Muon collider, proton based	68	3.51	0.88
Muon collider, positron based	65	3.50	0.80
Energy Recovery (>50 GeV and/or > 50 mA)	65	3.35	0.78
Crystal bending	55	3.30	0.68
Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms including gravity-based schemes	35	3.23	1.22
Gravitational wave detection using storage rings	49	3.23	1.05
Gamma Factory	60	3.19	0.70
Gravitational wave generation using accelerators	44	3.14	1.12
Crystalline beams	47	3.07	0.92

High energy photon generation using entanglement and Moessbauer effect	35	3.06	0.95
Photon Collider	58	3.00	0.64

Finally, Table 6 examines the expected readiness time scale for the different techniques. Here, we see that energy recovery, crystal bending, Gamma Factory and crystalline beams are considered as essentially ready for implementation during the next 10-15 years. On the other end, non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing, Moessbauer effect, and gravitational wave generation are expected to be ready on a 40-year time scale. Muon colliders are forecast about 20 years from now.

Table 6: Time scale for readiness - number of votes, average count (1: next 5 years, 5: next 100 years – see Table 1) and rms spread.

Future Options	votes	average	rms
Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms including gravity-based schemes	35	4.21	0.88
High energy photon generation using entanglement and Moessbauer effect	35	3.76	0.89
Gravitational wave generation using accelerators	44	3.70	0.92
Muon collider, positron based	65	3.30	0.93
Gravitational wave detection using storage rings	49	3.19	0.99
Muon collider, proton based	68	3.10	0.90
Crystal or nanostructure acceleration	55	2.98	1.07
Photon Collider	58	2.98	0.84
Plasma Acceleration	67	2.85	1.00
Crystalline beams	47	2.63	1.11
Gamma Factory	60	2.58	0.82
Crystal bending	55	2.04	1.05
Energy Recovery (>50 GeV and/or > 50 mA)	65	1.95	0.74

Figures 4, 5 and 6 display the results in a two-dimensional format, namely in the “Priority versus Societal Impact,” “Feasibility versus Priority” and “Feasibility versus Societal Impact” planes, respectively. Figure 7 illustrates the expected time scales for realization. Graphical summaries of individual survey results are presented in the Appendix.

The coloured error-bars in these pictures graphically represent the level of uncertainty in the assessment, and as shown, for every category ranking, this uncertainty spreads over the two-neighbour ranking. These results indicate that, although there is a preferred ranking, we still face a significant margin of uncertainty. This is not surprising as many of the far-future options presented require assessments of technologies not yet available and the participants of the survey respond to this unknown in different ways according to their experience, implicit biases, and their individual tendency to be more optimistic or more pessimistic.

Figure 4: Survey results in the Importance/Priority versus Societal Impact plane – average rating and rms spread are shown. The labels correspond to abbreviations for the various options (Non-EM: non-electromagnetic acceleration & focusing, Cry_NSA: Crystal and nanostructure acceleration, etc.)

Figure 5: Survey results in the Feasibility versus Importance/Priority plane – average rating and rms spread are shown. The labels correspond to abbreviations for the various options (Non-EM: non-electromagnetic acceleration and focusing, Cry_NSA: Crystal and nanostructure acceleration, GWGA: Gravitational Wave Generation using Accelerators, ER: Energy Recovery, PA: Plasma Acceleration, etc.)

Figure 6: Survey results in the Feasibility versus Societal Impact plane – average rating and rms spread are shown. The labels correspond to abbreviations for the various options (Non-EM: non-electromagnetic acceleration and focusing, Cry_NSA: Crystal and nanostructure acceleration, GWGA: Gravitational Wave Generation using Accelerators, ER: Energy Recovery, PA: Plasma Acceleration, etc.)

Figure 7: Expected realization time scale for the different options, according to the survey. The labels again correspond to abbreviations for the various options (Non-EM: non-electromagnetic acceleration and focusing, Cry_NSA: Crystal and nanostructure acceleration, GWGA: Gravitational Wave Generation using Accelerators, ER: Energy Recovery, PA: Plasma Acceleration, etc.)

6. Conclusions: Interpretation & Recommendation

The **highest priority and importance** are assigned to the proton-based muon collider, plasma acceleration, positron-based muon collider, and crystal or nanostructure acceleration. All of these are envisioned to be realized **on a 20-year time scale**. These also are the four options offering the highest potential return to society, with plasma and crystal/nanostructure acceleration at the top, followed by the two muon colliders. They are all considered technically hard to achieve. In the next three paragraphs, we review the main issues related to these top-ranked future options.

Muon colliders promise the most energy-efficient and lowest-cost path to lepton collision energies beyond 3 TeV – arguably the only affordable path to a future highest-energy lepton collider^{14,23}. A proton-based muon collider produces muons by smashing high-intensity proton beams onto a target, and capturing muons resulting from the decay of the produced pions. Due to their creation process, the muons initially occupy a large phase space volume. The proton-based muon collider concept then relies on very fast and efficient ionization cooling to increase the space-space density by a factor $\sim 10^6$. The principle of ionization cooling was demonstrated by the MICE experiment in the UK, but essentially with single muons, for which the effective central phase space density was increased by 10 or 20 percent²⁴, far from the factor $\sim 10^6$ ultimately necessary. A future demonstration experiment, required before a collider could be constructed, could be based on a more intense muon beam and would aim for a higher density increase, possibly using the advanced technique of parametric ionization cooling²³. The final cooling channel calls for strong focusing solenoids with a field of tens of Tesla, as could be realized by a high-field superconductor, still to be developed. The proton-based muon collider was designed and developed in some detail by the US MAP collaboration. An alternative positron-based muon production generates 22 GeV muon pairs by the annihilation of ~ 45 GeV positron with electrons at rest¹³. Production just above threshold ensures a small muon emittance without the need for ionization cooling. However, the cross section for annihilation is small, and multiple scattering during repeated passages through the target, of both positron beams and generated muons, leads to non-negligible emittance growth¹². Target design and muon accumulation require more R&D. The basic feasibility of this concept has not been fully demonstrated. For either type of muon collider rapid acceleration of the muons is the key. Fast ramping magnets with ramp speed above 10 T/s are one of the options suggested^{14,23}. Eddy currents in magnets and vacuum chambers need to be studied. In the collider ring itself the average luminosity is directly proportional to the field of the bending magnets, which represents another need for high field magnets. Muon colliders require a high flux of high-quality muons, which may find many other applications, e.g. for investigations of surfaces, superconductors, molecular systems, chemical reactions, novel battery materials, hydrogen behaviour, etc.²⁵

Plasmas can sustain field gradients of tens of GV per meter. They offer much higher accelerating gradients than conventional accelerators²⁶. The plasma fields can be excited by a laser, by an electron beam or by a proton beam. The number of particles per bunch are relatively low, as only a limited amount of energy is stored inside a plasma “bubble”, and beam quality is typically (much) worse²⁷ than for conventional accelerators. A priority of plasma acceleration R&D is improving beam quality and pulse-to-pulse beam stability. Collider concepts based on plasma often result in low to moderate luminosity, at the 10^{28} cm⁻²s⁻¹ level (six orders of magnitude lower than the LHC, eight orders of

magnitude lower than the design values of SuperKEKB or FCC-ee), and, as such, can only address a few (possibly, rather “marginal” or exotic) physics topics²⁸.

Crystals or nanostructures, thanks to their much higher density, allow for much higher fields than plasmas still, at the TV/m level or higher^{17,29,30}. The crystals could be excited by x-ray lasers^{29,30}. The volumes of the crystal channels or nanostructures are even much smaller than plasma bubbles, and particle bunches accelerated in a crystal or nanostructure will be of extremely low charge. Crystal-based collider concepts may require funnelling prior to collision to accomplish a decent luminosity. R&D is still in its infancy. Despite the challenges for collider applications, plasma or crystal-based accelerators hold the promise of potentially replacing conventional accelerators by much more compact ones, e.g. for medical and industrial applications³¹.

Another 20-year option is detecting gravitational waves (GWs) using storage rings^{21,32}, the feasibility and potential of which still requires further investigations. If proven feasible, storage rings could open up entirely new GW frequency windows²¹, compared with large laser interferometers like LIGO or VIRGO, contributing to this revolutionary science, that can shed light on the early history of the universe.

For the coming 10-15 years the community expects to see the advent of high-energy high-current accelerators with energy recovery³³, deployment of crystal bending¹⁶ and the Gamma Factory^{10,11}. These options are considered the most feasible and of lowest risk. Their importance is between relevant and high. In addition, they also promise a moderate to strong return to society. We will now discuss these three options in a little greater detail.

These three options are far advanced in their development and readiness. Energy recovery has been demonstrated at a few places, JLAB and Cornell in the US, and Daresbury in the UK, typically with beam current of the order the 0.1 mA level (with the exception of the “JLAB IR FEL Driver”, that reached 8 mA at 165 MeV beam energy³⁴), and in a single loop. Multi-pass energy recovery linacs (ERLs) at 10s of mA beam current (implying >100 mA currents passing through the multi-cell SC RF cavities) or 10s of GeV beam energy, as required for future collider projects, have not yet been demonstrated. A demonstration project, PERLE³⁵, is under construction at Orsay in France, and might see first beam from the injector in less than 5 years. Demonstration of PERLE ERL operation at 250 MeV is planned for 2028, and the full energy of 500 MeV shall be reached by 2030. Other projects, like MESA and BerlinPro in Germany, are nearing completion. High-luminosity high-energy upgrades based on the ERL concept are also proposed for the future circular e^+e^- collider FCC-ee – where it could push up collision energies from 365 GeV up to 550 GeV range³⁶, allowing double Higgs production and direct access to the top Higgs coupling –and for future linear colliders³⁷. As sustainable energy usage becomes ever more important the ERL concept could offer great societal benefits also for many other linear accelerator applications. The effective magnetic field of a bent crystal can reach 1000s of Tesla³⁸. Halo particle extraction from a storage ring using bent crystals was demonstrated already in the 1990s. After successful beam experiments at the LHC, a few crystal collimators are included in the baseline of the High Luminosity LHC upgrade, which will start operation around 2026. The Gamma Factory (GF)^{10,11} is based on storing partially stripped heavy ion beams in the LHC and exciting the ion electrons by a laser. Due to a double Lorentz boost, the energy of the re-emitted photon, is $4\gamma^2$ higher than the laser photon energy, where γ is the ion Lorentz factor.

Photon energies of order 100 MeV can be reached at a rate of $\sim 10^{17}$ photons/s, opening up many new areas of science. The GF could produce positrons and muons at unprecedented rates. A partially stripped heavy ion beam has already been successfully accelerated to top energy in the LHC with a beam lifetime of ~ 50 hours³⁹. Tests of laser ion collisions are planned in the CERN SPS during the coming years, paving the way to a future installation in the LHC itself. According to its proponents, the proper GF research programme at the LHC could start around the year 2032¹⁰.

Lowest priority and lowest potential return to society is attributed to the photon collider⁷, to crystalline beams²⁰, to “Moessbauer acceleration” using photon entanglement²², to gravitational wave generation using accelerators^{21,40,41}, and to non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing²². The last two options “non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms including gravity-based schemes” and “gravitational wave detection using storage rings” would also have a moderate to strong potential return to society. The latter has a priority close to high, the former one of the lowest priorities overall.

We briefly inspect these last options. The physics potential of photon colliders is rather limited compared with lepton colliders. Therefore, traditionally such colliders have been always only proposed as an “add-on” to an electron-positron collider⁴². This same consideration also limits the value of “Moessbauer acceleration” for the production of high-energy photons²². Low-energy ultracold crystalline beams have been produced, stored and studied, at a few places, notably at the electrostatic ring PALLAS in Munich²⁰, but so far, they have suffered a niche existence, and lacked any relevant applications. Using a crystalline beam in a storage ring for a more sensitive detection of gravitational waves, benefiting from the ordered structure and from such a beam’s wide phonon excitation spectrum, could still be of interest. Finally, accelerators – e.g., a 50 TeV hadron storage ring like the one of FCC-hh – could be among the most powerful terrestrial sources of GWs^{40,41}. If all beam particles and bunches contribute coherently the effect can be significant and measurable⁴¹. Presently theoretical predictions have not yet converged, and, hence, further fundamental studies and simulations are required, before this approach can be pursued in practice. Gravitational deflection of relativistic particles is a long-known consequence of Einstein’s theory of general relativity⁴³. Gravitational lensing of light⁴⁴ has been well established, and exploited, in astrophysical studies. Realizing so advanced a focusing method or a similarly innovative gravity/mini-black-hole based acceleration scheme^{22,45} on earth appears extremely daunting, even though the Mont Blanc mountain is already predicted to have a tiny effect on the revolution time of particles in the LHC. Based on present knowledge, such approaches might be put to practical use only in case of far-future large-scale extra-terrestrial accelerators.

Based on the community survey results, we can assemble the recommendations of Table 7. ARIES recommends following the prioritization given by the community.

Table 7: Recommended priority and focus for near-term and longer-term R&D.

Time scale	Priority and focus
10-15 years	Energy recovery Crystal bending Gamma Factory
15-30 years	Proton based muon collider Plasma acceleration Positron based muon collider Crystal and nanostructure acceleration Gravitational wave detection using storage rings
	Low or no priority
	Photon collider Crystalline beams “Moessbauer acceleration” using photon entanglement Gravitational wave generation using accelerators Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms

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Appendix: Graphical Display of Survey Results for Each Future Option

The individual survey results for each of the 13 options are displayed in Figs. 8-20 below.

Figure 8: Survey result for Energy Recovery (>50 GeV and/or > 50 mA)^{1,2,3}

Figure 9: Survey result for Plasma Acceleration^{4,5,6}

Figure 10: Survey result for Photon Collider^{7,8,9}

Figure 11: Survey result for Gamma Factory^{10,11}

Figure 12: Survey result for Muon Collider, positron based^{12,13}

Figure 13: Survey result for Muon Collider, proton based^{14,15}

Figure 14: Survey result for Crystal or Nanostructure Acceleration^{16,17,18}

Figure 15: Survey result for Crystal Bending^{16,19}

Figure 16: Survey result for Crystalline Beams²⁰

Figure 17: Survey result for Gravitational Wave Detection using Storage Rings²¹

Figure 18: Survey result for Gravitational Wave Generation using Accelerators²¹

Figure 19: Survey result for High Energy Photon Generation using Entanglement and Moessbauer Effect²²

Figure 20: Survey result for Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms including gravity based schemes²²